

Research Article

Sustainable Innovation in Paving Block Production: Using Semi - Crushed Shell and Semi - Concrete Waste

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Abstract: This study actually explores the innovative use of semi-crushed shells and semi-construction waste as a partial replacement for sand in the production of paving blocks. Addressing the challenges of diminishing natural sand resources and increasing construction waste. The objective here is to evaluate the feasibility of using alternative materials with particle sizes of 4.75mm to 0.15mm, which are commonly found in concrete mixtures, to maintain or improve the structural integrity of paving blocks while promoting sustainable construction practices. Concrete mixtures with a ratio of 1:2:4 were tested with sand replacements of 0%, 5% (2.5% shell powder and 2.5% construction waste powder) and 10% (5.0% shell powder and 5.0% construction waste powder). The results of the slump test showed a decrease in workability with increasing percentage of replacement with the result values being 14.01mm, 10.00mm and 7.99mm respectively. Despite this reduction, all mixtures remained within the acceptable actual slump range. To ensure sufficient workability for pavement applications. In particular, the compressive strength test showed that the 5% replacement mixture achieved the highest compressive strength of 45.41 MPa at 28 days, which outperformed the control mixture. This shows that using this alternative material can improve the quality of concrete while conserving natural resources and managing waste effectively. This innovation reduces environmental impact, which promotes the use of high-quality waste and is in line with the goal of sustainable construction. This solution shows potential for commercialization for the construction industry, especially in producing non-structural paving blocks. Recognizing this innovation, the study has advanced to the final stage of the "Joint Proposal Defense Session of the TRANS-TECH 4TVET Grant Technical Committee 2025" and won third place at the INNOTEX DCE Polytechnic Kota Bharu Exhibition 2024.

Keywords: sustainable construction; alternative materials; paving blocks

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1. INTRODUCTION

The introduction highlights the growing demand for sustainable innovation in the construction industry. Excessive sand mining has caused significant environmental degradation, such as soil erosion and habitat loss (Koehnken, 2020). The use of semi-crushed shells and semi construction waste as a partial replacement for sand with a size between 4.75mm and 0.15mm in paving blocks provides an environmentally friendly solution to this challenge. This study also focuses on evaluating the feasibility of a structure and environment in which this approach is implemented while aligning with global sustainable construction goals (Mohammed, 2023). In addition, various mechanical tests such as drop and compression tests were conducted in this study. This research offers empirical evidence of the potential of this waste material to effectively replace sand while maintaining or even improving the structural properties of paving blocks. Therefore, this article discusses innovations in using semi-crushed shells and construction concrete waste as replacement materials in the construction industry,

where it focuses on reducing environmental impact and also improving resource efficiency in the production of paving blocks.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

Material Preparation this study actually used seashells obtained from seafood industry waste and concrete waste from building demolition sites. While both materials were cleaned and crushed using a crushing machine to obtain the appropriate particle size (Koehnken, 2020). The particle size for seashells and concrete waste was in the range of 0.15 mm to 4.75 mm, which is the standard size of sand for concrete mixtures (Rahman, 2021). Seashells were collected from seafood processing areas, while concrete waste was obtained from local construction sites (Mohammed, 2023). The mixture design involved three sand replacement ratios namely: 0% (control mixture), 5%, and 10% replacement using a combination of semi-crushed seashells and semi-crushed concrete waste. The mixture was produced with a ratio of 1:2:4 (cement: sand: coarse aggregate). Which is the standard ratio in the production of paving blocks (Chen, 2023). Each mixture was tested to evaluate mechanical performance which includes compressive strength and workability (Tam, 2023). The replacement ratio of 5% and 10% was chosen based on previous studies that showed that replacing part of the sand with waste materials can improve the properties of concrete (López-Uceda, 2022). Test Procedure have two test such as: (i) Compression Test: Compression tests were performed using a compression machine to measure the compressive strength of the paving blocks after a hardening period of 28 days (Zhang, 2022). This test was conducted according to ASTM C39 standards to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the data (Bao & Lu, 2023). (ii) Slump Test: The workability of the concrete mixture was tested using a slump test. The slump value reflects the ability of the concrete mix to flow without losing integrity (Rahman, 2021). The results of this test will be analysed to identify the most suitable mix in terms of mechanical performance and environmental sustainability.

3. FINDINGS

The results of this study show that the use of crushed shell and construction waste as a partial substitute for sand in the production of paving blocks is viable. The main results obtained from the tests carried out are as follows:

Figure 1. Slump test is being done near the laboratory.

Table 1. Slump Test Results according to the mixing ratio of 0%, 5% and 10%

No.	Mix Percent (%)	Fall Rate (mm)
1.	0	14.01
2.	5	10.00
3.	10	7.99

Figure 2. Compression Test is being done at the laboratory.

Table 2. Sample compression test results

Mix percent	Average Compressive Strength (MPa-14 days)	Average Compressive Strength (MPa-28 Days)
0%	31.17	38.99
5%	36.81	45.41
10 %	35.04	37.79
Specifications	25.60	25.60

3.1 Slump Test

Figure 3. The results of the slump test

The results from table 1 and figure 3: where the slump test results showed that the workability of the concrete mixture decreased with increasing percentage of sand replacement. The recorded slump values were as follows: 14.01 mm fall rate for the mix with 0% replacement, while 10.00 mm fall rate for 5% replacement and 7.99 mm for 10% replacement. Despite the reduction in slump values, all mixes remained within the "true slump" range, indicating acceptable workability for pavement concrete applications. This highlights the viability of using alternative materials such as crushed shell and construction waste without affecting the workability of the mixture.

3.2 Compression Test

Figure 4 (a). The results of the compression test (14 Days)

Figure 4 (b). The results of the compression test (28 Days)

The results from table 2 and figure 4(a): At 14 days, the compressive strength of the control mix (0% replacement) was 31.17 MPa, while the 5% and 10% replacements recorded 36.81 MPa and 35.04 MPa, respectively. At 28 days, the compressive strength improved to 38.99 MPa for the control mix, 45.41 MPa for the 5% replacement, and 37.79 MPa for the 10% replacement. The 5% replacement mix showed the highest compressive strength increase (25.36%), indicating optimal performance at this level of substitution.

4. DISCUSSION

Figure 4. Analysis Compression Strength of Paving Blocks

Figure 5. Among the eco-friendly concrete products are those that combine seashells and waste materials such as recycled concrete waste.

The findings suggest that replacing up to 10% of sand with crushed shell and construction waste does not compromise the compressive strength of the paving blocks. The 5% replacement mix not only meets but exceeds the minimum industry standard for compressive strength, making it the most promising for practical applications. "The use of recycled materials such as recycled concrete construction waste and partially crushed shells not only reduces dependence on natural resources but also significantly contributes to more sustainable and environmentally friendly construction practices (Ahn et al., 2020; Bhattacharjee et al., 2021; Khalaf et al., 2020)." These results validate the potential of using crushed shell and concrete waste to produce environmentally sustainable paving blocks with structural integrity comparable to conventional ones. The study highlights the dual benefits of this innovation, including effective waste management and conservation of natural sand resources.

5. CONCLUSION

The study titled "Sustainable Innovation in Pavement Block Production: Using Half-Concrete Shells and Half-Concrete Waste" underscores the feasibility of employing crushed shells and construction waste as partial substitutes for sand in paving block production. The results indicate that this alternative material can produce paving blocks with compressive strength that matches or even surpasses that of conventional blocks, making it particularly suitable for non-structural applications. The research identifies an optimal mix with a 5% sand replacement, achieving an excellent balance between mechanical properties and workability, while meeting established industry standards for paving block applications. This approach offers promising potential for advancing sustainable construction practices. Nevertheless, further investigation is necessary to evaluate the long-term durability and scalability of this method, particularly under diverse environmental conditions and extended usage periods, Bao and Lu (2023).

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